

MICROSTRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF TiBCN-Ti-6Al-4V BASE
COMPOSITES PREPARED BY LASER CLADDING

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Keywords: TiBCN powder; Ti-6Al-4V base composite; microstructure; hardness;
wear resistance

ABSTRACT

TiBCN powder, possessing NaCl-type fcc structure, synthesized by boronizing of Ti, was firstly used as additives to make TiBCN-Ti-6Al-4V base composites on Ti-6Al-4V by laser cladding. The TiBCN powders and Mn powders were used to make powder mixtures with contents of 90TiBCN+10 Mn, 80TiBCN+20 Mn, 70TiBCN+30Mn, and 60TiBCN+40 Mn. Behavior of TiBCN particles in the TiBCN-Ti-6Al-4V base composites were evaluated by SEM(scanning electron microscopy), EDS (energy dispersive spectroscopy), and XRD(X-ray diffraction). It was found that TiBCN particles were partially melted during cladding and they were self organized as dendrite structures in laser clad layer. Al was dissolved in TiBCN to form Ti(Al)BCN. Maximum hardness of TiBCN- Ti-6Al-4V base composite was up to HV1200 and its wear resistance was increased by a factor of 4 compared to that of substrate. The studies have demonstrated that the TiBCN powder is an available material for fabricating metal matrix composite, especially for Ti-6Al-4V base alloys.

1 INTRODUCTION

Titanium alloys such as Ti - 6Al - 4V have widely been utilized in aerospace, petro-chemical and bio-implant applications because of their high strength-to-weight ratio and an excellent corrosion resistance. However, a poor wear resistance of this alloy creates problem for its wider application. Laser cladding has been employed to enhance the wear resistance of titanium and its alloys by reinforcing outer layer of Ti alloys with ceramic particles. The ceramic particles used for the purpose include in situ precipitated orthorhombic TiB [1], WC [2], TiB₂ [3], TiC [4-5], Al₂O₃ [6], fcc-TiB [7] and Y₂O₃ [8]. TiB reinforced Ti-alloy composites combine the high strength and stiffness of the borides with the toughness and damage tolerance of the Ti-alloy matrix and offer attractive properties such as increased stiffness, enhanced elevated temperature strength, good creep performance, fatigue resistance and wear resistance. It is likely that Titanium borides are much available for fabricating Ti based composites [9-10].

Recently, TiBCN powder with high hardness and good corrosion resistance was synthesized by means of boronizing of Ti [7]. It possesses NaCl-type structure like fcc-TiB (PDF card No.06-0641) as confirmed by analysis of XRD and TEM diffraction in which B, C and N occupy the same points of crystal lattice as Cl in NaCl.

Study of using TiBCN powder as additive has not well been carried out so far. In this work, TiBCN powder is used as additive with Mn powder to enhance the strength and wear resistance of Ti - 6Al - 4V by laser cladding. Microstructure and wear resistance of the Ti-6Al-4V base composites reinforced with TiBCN powder by laser cladding are evaluated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS AND PROCEDURES

TiBCN powder used for laser cladding was synthesized by means of boronizing of Ti, supplied by Changchun Domgji Materials and Science Co. Ltd.. Fig.1 presents morphology for TiBCN powder and its chemical and physical properties are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Chemical and physical properties of TiBCN powder

Features	TiBCN
purity	98.5%
Melting point	2900°C
Color	Yellow brawn
Crystal structure	NaCl-type fcc; space group Fm-3m
Lattice parameter	0.4241nm
Electrical resistivity	$15 \times 10^{-7} \Omega \cdot m$
Corrosion resistance	No react with HSO ₄ and HNO ₃

Fig.1 SEM Morphology of TiBCN powder

Fig.2 XRD spectra of TiBCN powder, showing that the TiBCN powder possesses NaCl-type fcc crystal structure

TiBCN powder (-200 mesh) and Mn powder (-200 mesh) were mixed according to a series of ratio of TiBCN to Mn 90 to 10, 80 to 20, 70 to 30 and 60 to 40, respectively. The samples with the size of 10 mm × 5 mm × 50 mm were machined from Ti-6Al-4V plates. Subsequently, the slots of 4 mm width and 3 mm depth were made on the samples for holding the powder mixtures. The mixtures were filled into the slots, followed by pressing the powder mixtures to dense.

A 5 kW CO₂ laser was used to carry out cladding, operated at a output power of 4000 W and beam diameter of 4 mm. The samples were mounted on a x-y table, moving at a speed of 0.6m /min. under the laser beam. Ar gas was used to protect coating from oxidation. Scanning Electron microscope (SEM, model JSM5310 equipped with EDS) was employed to characterize microstructure and composition of the laser clad samples.

XRD diffractometer, model Rigaku D/max-2400X, was used to detect both crystal structure of laser clad layer, operated at voltage 50 kV, current 300 mA, scanning speed 4deg/min and scanning range of 20° -100°. A microhardness tester, model HVS-1000, was used to check hardness, at a load of 2.94 N and holding time of 20 s. The hardness values given in this study are average values of three measurements.

The slices used for wear testing were cut from laser clad layers along direction parallel to the surface and then the disks with a diameter of 3 mm were cut from the slices, followed by thinning their thicknesses to 700 nm. Wear tests were carried out on a dimpling instrument

commonly used for dimpling TEM specimen prior ion milling as shown in Fig. 3. The prepared discs were glued on the platform. They were worn by a steel wheel mounted on the arm, running at a speed of 80 r/min under a load of 160 g. The platform was automatically revolved at a speed of 10 r/min. Each fraction wheel was used for one time only.

Fig.3 Scheme of wear test

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Microstructure

Fig.4 present the scheme of samples before laser cladding and SEM image of laser clad layer. The powder mixtures consisting of TiBCN and Mn powder in the slots were irradiated by laser beam along the direction of slot, forming a sunken layer resulted from the contraction of laser clad region. The densification of powder mixtures occurred during cladding, leading to the decrease of thickness of powder mixtures from 3 mm to 2 mm. Furthermore, original boundary between the powder mixtures and substrate was found to be removed from 2 mm to 0.3 mm towards the bottom direction of sample. This enlargement of laser clad region indicates that the substrate was fully melted and the powders was well mixed with the melt. The laser clad Ti-6Al-4V can be divided into clad layer, boundary, heat affect region and substrate, respectively. Heat affect region is narrow. The laser clad layer appeared as dendrite structure. In which the TiBCN particles were homogeneously dispersed. The hardness of laser clad layer was measured to be in the range of HV700-900, increasing by a factor of 3 compared to that of substrate(hardness of substrate is about HV330). In laser clad layer, small amount of pores exist, but there is no any cracks.

Fig.4 Scheme of samples before laser cladding and SEM image of laser clad layer, TiBCN 80%+Mn 20%

Fig.5 Element mapping images of laser clad layer, TiBCN 80%+Mn20%

Fig.5 show the dendrite structure and its element distribution obtained by mapping of EDS. It is known from distribution of Ti and N that the TiBCN particles were located within dendrite structure surrounded by some new phases and β -Ti. It is interesting to note that the TiBCN phases were self-organized to follow the profile of dendrite. In addition, Al was dissolved in TiBCN to form Ti(Al)BCN as confirmed by the element mapping images in which distribution Al and N is similar. It was reported that Ti(Al)N was formed by the incorporation of Al into TiN during deposition [11]. This supports our present result. It is anticipated that high temperature properties of TiBCN can be improved by the incorporation of Al in TiBCN.

It is thought that TiBCN particles were partially melted during cladding and were self organized to form dendrite on cooling. The melt surrounding partially melted TiBCN particles consisted of very complex compositions coming from melted TiBCN particles, Mn particles and matrix as well. Some new phases were precipitated from such melt on cooling.

Fig.6 XRD spectra of laser clad layer

Fig.6 shows XRD spectra for the laser clad layer. It is identified that the detected phases include TiBCN, TiN_{0.2}, Al₃Ti, TiAl, MnB and TiB₂. The TiBCN is the additive which underwent partially melted and TiN_{0.26}, Al₃Ti, TiAl, MnB and TiB₂ are in situ formed novel phases. The XRD spectra demonstrate that crystal structure of TiBCN remained unchanged even though partially melting of which occurred on laser cladding, indicating that TiBCN is available reinforcement additive for enhancing the strength of Ti-6Al-4V.

Fig.7 (a) illustrates microstructure for laser clad layer in details. It can be seen that partially melted TiBCN particles are well connected one by one to form dendrite-like structure. The Ti metal between dendrite structure was moved away by erosion solution. It is clear that TiBCN in laser clad layer have very good corrosion resistance. As shown in Fig.7(b), microstructure in boundary zone is identified as quenched Ti alloy without any TiBCN particles.

Fig.7 SEM images, showing microstructure in laser clad layer and in boundary zone, (a) dendrite-like structure (b) quenched Ti alloy in boundary, TiBCN 95%

3.2 Influence of content of TiBCN on hardness of laser clad layer

Microhardness values of laser clad layers for the samples containing different contents of TiBCN were measured along their cross sections.

Fig.8 illustrates relationship between microhardness and contents of TiBCN powder for different samples. For the samples with TiBCN 60%, 80%, 90% , 95% and 100% , the values of microhardness increase with increasing contents in the laser clad depths less than 1.26mm and then decreased. All of the samples have a maximum value at a depth of 1.26um, indicating the laser clad depth is about 1.26um. The levels of microhardness at the same depths for different samples are in a order of 80% > 90% > 95% > 100% > 60%. The levels of microhardness values for the samples with TiBCN 60% and 100% are almost the same. The reason for the decreased microhardness for TiBCN 100% is because the TiBCN particles were not well combined due to absence of adhesive metals. The reason for the sample with TiBCN 60% is less particles in laser clad layer compared to TiBCN 80%, 90% and 95%. The maximum microhardness of 1300HV appeared at the sample of TiBNC 80%. The maximum microhardness of 1300HV appeared at the sample of TiBNC 80%.

Fig. 8 Variation of microhardness with contents of TiBCN

The hardness tests were also carried out along direction parallel to the surface. For this purpose, the slices were cut from the laser clad layers as shown in Fig.8(a) and followed by hardness testing along the dish lines as shown in Fig.9(b).

Fig. 9 Schematic illustration of sample cutting and hardness testing position, (a)scheme of slice cutting from laser clad layer,(b) position for hardness testing(dash line)

Fig. 10 Microstructural hardness distribution of the cladding coating with different content of TiBCN Fig.10 presents the distributions of microhardness along dish lines for the samples with different contents. All of which exhibit their maximum values in the middle of the line. The samples with TiBCN 80%,90% and 95% possess higher hardness compared to samples with 60% and 100%. The reason of hardness lowering for TiBCN 60% is because of less particles and the decreased hardness for the sample with 100% is thought to be attributed to less adhesive metals in the laser clad layer. The sample with TiBCN 80% exhibits the higher hardness values compared to 90% , 95% , 100% and 60% respectively. It is clear that the most of hardness values in the middle of the layer are between 700HV and 1100HV, much higher than HV 320 of substrate .

3.3 Influence of content of TiBCN on wear resistance

The crater grinder was employed to check wear resistance of laser clad layers for different samples. The diameters of the worn craters for samples containing TiBCN 90%, 80% and 60% were shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Relationship between content of TiBCN and diameter of worn crater

TiBCN contents	90%	80%	60%	substrate
Crater diameter	1.1 mm	0.9 mm	1.1 mm	2.0 mm
Wear loss	1.08 mg	0.56 mg	1.06 mg	2.06 mg

It can be seen that the diameter of the sample with TiBCN content of 90%, 80% and 60% are all smaller than that of substrate. Fig. 11 presents the morphology of the worn craters for different samples. It is noted that the sample with TiBCN 80% has a smallest diameter of worn crater while the substrate has largest one. This variation tendency of worn diameters for different samples is similar with that of variation of hardness with TiBCN contents. The enhanced wear resistance for the samples with TiBCN 80% exhibiting is thought to be attributed to its high hardness.

Fig. 11 The low SEM images of worn surface of the clad layer with different content of TiBCN: (a) 90%, (b) 80%, (c) 60% and (d) the substrate

Fig.12 presents morphology of worn surface of craters, revealed by a series of SEM images, for samples with TiBCN 90%, 80% and 60%. The worn surface of substrate is characterized by large grooves and adhesive scars, indicating that the substrate suffered severe friction and wear by means of ploughing and scratching and adhesive can be thought as main mechanisms for the wear of substrate. However, the laser clad samples have demonstrated good worn morphology with only small amounts of pits and shallow ploughing grooves and adhesive phenomenon is not severe. The reason for the enhanced wear resistance is attributed to the addition of TiBCN into laser clad layer. This is because the layer reinforced with TiBCN possesses high hardness and high resistant to wear.

Fig. 12 SEM images of worn surface of the clad layer with different content of TiBCN: (a) 90%, (b) 80%, (c) 60% and (d) the substrate

Fig. 13 EDS analysis of worn surface of 60% TiBCN cladding coating

Fig. 13 shows EDS element mapping results for the worn surface of sample with TiBCN 60% TiBCN +40% Mn. Ti,Al,V and N are homogeneously dispersed in the worn surface. N mapping is resulted from N in TiBCN, indicating the existence of TiBNC reinforcements in the worn surface. it is interesting to note that in the worn surface Fe exists as revealed by element analysis. This result indicates that Fe was removed from friction wheel made from steel to the worn surface during wearing. This Fe was transported from the friction wheel to the worn surface. It is showed by wear testing that the laser clad layer exhibited much better wear resistance than that of friction wheel.

Fig. 14 shows variation of wear loss with different samples. Wear losses of laser clad layers with TiBCN reinforcements is increased by a factor of 4 compared to that of substrate. The wear loss of sample with TiBCN 80% has demonstrated the minimum wear loss.

Fig. 14 Wear loss of the substrate and clad layer with different TiBCN contents

4 CONCLUSIONS

1, TiBCN-Ti-6Al-4V matrix coatings on Ti-6Al-4V were successfully fabricated by laser cladding. TiBCN particles were partially melted during cladding and were finally formed as dendrite structure at room temperature.

2, The hardness values of TiBCN-Ti-6Al-4V matrix coatings increase with increasing content of TiBCN. A maximum value of HV 1200 was obtained at 80% TiBCN, increasing by a factor of 4 as compared with that of substrate (HV320).

3, The wear resistance of TiBCN-Ti-6Al-4V matrix coatings prepared by laser cladding was increased by a factor 4 as compared with that of substrate. Wear loss decrease with increasing content of TiBCN. The coating made with 80%TiBCN has overall shown lowest wear loss as compared with coatings fabricated with other ratio of TiBCN to Ti.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The project is financially supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 51172088). The authors thank Dr Yao Yuan and his assistants to allow to use their equipment to carry out laser cladding.

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